

Towards the discovery of a New Universal constant: Chromatic Circle & Life common Formula

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<https://montagnier.net/flm/fr/accueil/>

In 1997, 27 years ago, we discovered this beautiful formula (figures 1, 2 and 3) which, applied to all ATOMIC MASS of a constituent of the living (bioatoms C O N H S P... Nucleotide. DNA RNA, Amino Acids... Projected these masses on a numerical scale in multiple integers of $\pi/10$, unifying all the genetic, biological and genomic information of the bioatoms up to the whole genomes leading even to the emergence of NUMERICAL WAVES...

The formula (figures 1, 2, 3) at the heart of this projection is based on the universal constants π and Φ the golden number.

But more simply, its numerical value after calculation is $P = 0.742340663...$

This discovery has been the subject of dozens of articles which the 2 main are the book CODEX BIOGENESIS (2009)

https://www.amazon.fr/Codex-Biogenesis-13-codes-IADN/dp/2874340448/ref=asc_df_2874340448/?tag=googshopfr-21&linkCode=df0&hvadid=701628780643&hvpos=&hvnetw=g&hvrnd=13937336127459720749&hvpone=&hvptwo=&hvqmt=&hvdev=m&hvdvcmdl=&hvlocint=&hvlocphy=1006094&hvtargid=pla-458738363885&psc=1&mcid=24756b875a0831eea2d38a02cdf67d30&gad_source=1

Figure 1 – CODEX BIOGENESIS book

And this 2021 article prefaced by my friend RIP Pr Luc Montagnier, Nobel Prize winner discoverer of the HIV virus of AIDS.

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/SIX-FRACTAL-CODES-OF-LIFE-FROM-BIOATOMS-ATOMIC-MASS-Perez-Montagnier/b332d3eed4a2f554c233da2e07ec68daab9a2182>

coding multiples 1/10 regular values. These codes are called P-masses.

$$\text{Proj}(m) = 1 - [4\pi\sqrt{\varphi\varphi^2}] m$$

2008: *The EQUATION of LIFE...* by Jean-Claude Perez

with: $\sqrt{\varphi} = 1/\sqrt{\Phi}$ φ is the GOLDEN RATIO Φ
 $\varphi = 1/\Phi$
 $\varphi^2 = 1/\Phi^2$

Figure 1 The numerical projection formula of the atomic masses of any biological component.

Figure 2 – The P Universal constant project irregular atomic mass on a PI/10 regular numerical scale (Here all RNA, DNA and amino acids orange atomic mass are projected on regular images purple).

"Is there an EQUATION for LIFE?"

$S = I$

 $S = 4\pi R^2$
 with $R^2 = \sqrt{\varphi\varphi\varphi^2}$
 $R = \sqrt[3]{\varphi\varphi\varphi^2} = \varphi^{7/4}$
 Differentiating 2 projections of the atomic mass m
 - Projection on a CUBIC 3-D surface.
 - Projection on a SPHERIC 3-D surface.
 $Proj(m) = [1 - [4\pi\sqrt{\varphi\varphi\varphi^2}]]m = [1 - [4\pi\varphi^{7/2}]]m$
 with $\sqrt{\varphi-1} = 1/\varphi$
 $\varphi = 1 + \Phi$
 $\varphi^2 = 1 + \Phi^2$
 Phi is the GOLDEN RATIO Φ

(a)
 This universal formula process a differentiation or interference between both atomic mass "m" projections through a CUBE 2D surface of size 1x1x1 and a SPHERE of size $R = \varphi^{7/4}$
 The result is a common UNIFIED scale common to ALL organic compounds (DNA, RNA amino acids)...

Details in the book of J.C Perez CODEX BIOGENESIS:
<https://sites.google.com/site/codexbiogenesis/>

"The Periodic Table of Biology": evidence of a regular projection scale based on Pi/10 units.

(c) jcPerez's ORIGINofLIFE newCONSTRAINTS Average Mass OPTIMALITY vs Monoisotopes

Figure 3 – the Formula for Life (P value) based on Pi and Phi the golden ratio.

In a completely different field, that of light, we know the wavelengths of the 3 soft colors Blue, yellow and red.

The colors are represented on a Circle named Color Circle. (see <https://chimactiv.agroparistech.fr/en/bases/spectroscopie-uv/interpretation-spectre/4.>).

Figure 4 – The Chromatic Circle where yellow frontier 580nm and Blue frontier 430nm are diametrically opposed.

We also know that two complementary colours inhibit each other to create grey.

On this Circle 2 complementary colors are diametrically opposed as shown in figure 4

For example the 430nm blue/blue border and the 580nm jaube/orange gfrontiere are one of the major features of the Chromatic Circle.

Let's calculate the blue/yellow ratio:

$$430 / 580 = 0.74137931034$$

Now let's recall the P-values of our formula for life...

$$P = 0.742340663$$

Let us calculate the ratio of these two universal values, one in the Domain of life... And the

other in that of light...

$$0.742340 / 0.741379 = 1.0012962331$$

These 2 values are correlated with a precision of 1 millieme...

Let us reflect on the meaning of these two projections:

P applies to the frequency of the yellow wave shift of Pi to lead to the frequency of Blue wave.

P applied to an atomic mass of a component of the living project te on a digital regulize scale of multiples of Pi/10.

All this remains strange...

Bringing these two universes closer to the light and the living...

Figure 5 – Human Life RESONANCE and WAVES : Human complete Chromosome4
Chimpanzee complete chromosome4

(Resonance=34, Fibonacci number)

(Resonance=21, Fibonacci number)